

HOW TO ORGANIZE THE LESSON EFFECTIVELY

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Abstract. The article depicts the objectives for conducting an effective and exciting lesson for students. How to use unusual, interesting tasks in order to involve students to participate actively and keep their attention at the lessons.

Аннотация. Статья рассматривает задачи проведения эффективного и увлекательного урока для учащихся. Как использовать необычные, интересные задания, чтобы привлечь учащихся к активному участию и удерживать внимание на уроках.

Аннотация. Мақолада талабалар учун самарали ва қизиқарли дарс ўтказиш вазифалари кўрсатилган. Ўқувчиларни дарсга фаол жалб қилиш

учун ноодатий ва қизиқарли машғулотлардан қандай фойдаланиш усуллари кўрсатилган.

Keywords: Objectives; engaging activities: role-playing, debate and discussions, interactive games, media-based activities; varied instructional methods.

Ключевые слова: Цели; увлекательные задания: ролевые игры, дебаты и обсуждения, интерактивные игры, занятия с использованием медиа ресурсов; разнообразные методы обучения.

Калит сўзлар: Maqsadlar; qiziqarli topshiriqlar: rolli o'yinlar, bahs va munozaralar, interfaol o'yinlar, ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalangan holda tuzilgan topshiriqlar; turli xil o'qitish usullari.

Organizing a lesson effectively is crucial for engaging students, facilitating learning, and achieving educational goals. An effectively organized lesson typically involves clear objectives, engaging activities, varied instructional methods, and assessment strategies. It also considers the diverse needs of learners and encourages active participation. Effective lesson organization promotes student understanding, retention, and application of knowledge. This topic encompasses various aspects such as lesson planning, instructional design, classroom management, and student engagement techniques.

Creating an effective English lesson for intermediate level students involves careful planning and consideration of various factors such as clear objectives, engaging activities, and varied instructional methods. In this detailed description, we will explore each of these components in depth to help you design a comprehensive and engaging lesson

Clear Objectives:

Clear objectives are essential for guiding the teaching and learning process. When designing English lessons for intermediate level students, it's

important to set specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) objectives. These objectives should clearly outline what students are expected to learn by the end of the lesson. For example, a clear objective for an English lesson could be:

Objective: By the end of the lesson, students will be able to use past tenses correctly in spoken and written communication.

Having clear objectives helps both teachers and students stay focused on what needs to be achieved during the lesson. It provides a roadmap for instruction and assessment.

Engaging Activities:

Engaging activities are crucial for maintaining student interest and promoting active participation in the learning process. For intermediate level English students, incorporating a variety of activities can help cater to different learning styles and preferences. Here are some engaging activities that can be included in an English lesson:

1. **Role-Playing Scenarios:** Divide students into pairs or small groups and assign them different roles to act out real-life scenarios. This activity helps students practice speaking and listening skills in a practical context.

2. **Debates and Discussions:** Organize debates or group discussions on thought-provoking topics related to the lesson content. This activity encourages critical thinking, argumentation, and language fluency.

3. **Creative Writing Tasks:** Ask students to write short stories, poems, or dialogues based on a given prompt. This activity allows students to express their creativity while practicing writing skills.

4. **Interactive Games:** Incorporate language learning games such as word puzzles, vocabulary quizzes, or grammar challenges to make learning fun and engaging.

5. **Media-based Activities:** Use videos, songs, podcasts, or news articles to spark discussions, improve listening comprehension, and introduce cultural aspects of the English language.

For instance, we may see the following example for media-based activities:

Task Description:

- 1. Choose a current news article from a reputable news source.*
- 2. Read the article carefully and take notes on the main points, key facts, and any opinions presented.*
- 3. Write a summary of the article in your own words, focusing on the main idea and supporting details.*
- 4. Analyze the article by considering the following questions:*
 - What is the main message or purpose of the article?*
 - What sources are cited in the article? Are they reliable?*
 - Are there any biases or assumptions present in the article?*
 - How does the article make you feel? Do you agree or disagree with the points made?*
- 5. Present your analysis to the class or discuss it in small groups, sharing your insights and opinions.*

This kind of tasks can motivate the students to be more independent and awake their interest for further educational challenges.

By including a variety of engaging activities in the lesson plan, teachers can cater to different learning preferences and keep students motivated throughout the class.

Varied Instructional Methods:

Using varied instructional methods is essential for accommodating diverse learning styles and maximizing student engagement. Here are some effective instructional methods that can be incorporated into an English lesson for intermediate level students:

1. Direct Instruction: Provide clear explanations, examples, and demonstrations to introduce new concepts or language structures. Direct instruction helps build foundational knowledge and understanding.

2. Collaborative Learning: Encourage collaboration among students through group work, pair activities, or peer feedback sessions. Collaborative learning promotes communication skills, teamwork, and mutual support.

3. Differentiated Instruction: Adapt teaching strategies and materials to meet the individual needs and abilities of students. Differentiated instruction helps ensure that all students can access and benefit from the lesson content.

4. Scaffolded Learning: Break down complex tasks into smaller, manageable steps to support student learning progression. Scaffolding helps students build confidence and skills gradually.

It can be applied even for above-given task, when students can break the task for mini ones, and work in groups or in pairs where each member will be responsible for one exact part.

5. Inquiry-Based Learning: Encourage students to ask questions, explore topics independently, and discover answers through research and critical thinking. Inquiry-based learning fosters curiosity and self-directed learning.

By incorporating a mix of instructional methods in the lesson plan, teachers can create a dynamic and interactive learning environment that caters to the diverse needs of intermediate level English students.

In conclusion, designing an effective English lesson for intermediate level students requires careful consideration of clear objectives, engaging activities, and varied instructional methods. By setting clear learning goals, incorporating interactive activities, and using diverse teaching strategies, teachers can create a stimulating and inclusive learning experience that promotes language acquisition, critical thinking skills, and overall student engagement.

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